

Anaerobic seeding with suitable germplasm

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In wet direct seeding in the tropics, germinated seeds are usually broadcast onto well-puddled soil. Crop establishment is generally unstable because young seedlings on the soil surface are exposed to many biotic and abiotic stresses, such as desiccation caused by direct exposure to air, washing away by heavy rain, and bird damage. Seeding in flooded soil (anaerobic seeding) solves the constraints described above but requires germplasm with vigorous seedling growth under lack of oxygen.

We have identified varieties with tolerance for anaerobic seeding from the more than 1,000 varieties we have screened since 1989.

We tested three tolerant varieties in soils collected from the experimental fields of IRRI (Maahas, Mollisol) and PhilRice (Bantog, Vertisol) to see if seedling establishment ability in different flooded soils is a stable varietal trait. The upland soil was sieved with mesh 40. The lowland soils were taken from the flooded fields, passed through steel screen with 5-mm openings to remove debris, and placed in containers for 1 d before planting to settle the soil particles.

Seeds of tolerant varieties International Rice Germplasm Center accession 6267 (ASD1 from India), 9080 (JC178 from India), and 13746 (Thaothabi from India), and controls IR8, IR36, and IR50 were germinated for 2 d at 30 °C. Seventeen seeds/variety were planted in a row at a depth of 25 mm in containers (300 × 240 × 110 mm, with soil 80 mm deep). Soils were then submerged in 30 mm of water. The seedlings were grown in a temperature-controlled (29/21 °C day/night) glass room under natural light for 14 d during

Table 1. Seedling establishment from flooded soils.^a

Soil source	Control variety	Tolerant variety	Difference
<i>Emergence score</i>			
Lowland, Maahas	0.29 b	0.79 b	0.51*
Lowland, Bantog	0.56 b	1.35 b	0.79**
Upland, Maahas	2.38 a	4.24 a	1.86**
<i>Percent establishment</i>			
Lowland, Maahas	7.4 b	19.6 b	12.3*
Lowland, Bantog	16.2 b	34.8 b	18.6**
Upland, Maahas	53.9 a	89.2 a	35.3**
<i>Seedling height (mm)</i>			
Lowland, Maahas	7.9 b	34.0 b	26.1*
Lowland, Bantog	13.6 b	47.3 b	33.7**
Upland, Maahas	92.1 a	276.4 a	184.3**
<i>Mesocotyl length (mm)</i>			
Lowland, Maahas	0.30 b	2.04 b	1.74**
Lowland, Bantog	0.72 b	3.33 b	2.62**
Upland, Maahas	2.27 a	8.71 a	6.43**

^aFor each parameter, means in a column having a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. Differences are significant at the 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels.

Table 2. Correlation coefficient between the characters associated with seedling establishment.^a

Character	Percent establishment	Seedling height	Mesocotyl length	Rate of germination	Percent germination
Emergence score	1.00**	0.99**	0.99**	0.55 ns	0.57 ns
Percent establishment		0.98**	0.98**	0.58 ns	0.57 ns
Seedling height			0.98**	0.48 ns	0.53 ns
Mesocotyl length				0.61 ns	0.52 ns
Rate of germination					0.59 ns

^a*, ** = significant at 5 and 1% levels, respectively. ns = not significant.

1992 dry season. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications.

Emergence score, seedling height, and mesocotyl length were the mean for seedlings planted. Emergence score was recorded for individual seedlings as 0 = no emergence, 1 = coleoptile emerged on the soil surface, 2 = 1st leaf emerged, 3 = 2d leaf emerged, and so on.

The tolerant varieties had better emergence score, seedling height, and percent establishment in the three soils than did the controls (Table 1). Seedling establishment was better in Maahas upland soil, presumably because of higher redox potential, than in the lowland soils. Redox potential at

14 d after planting was 280 mV for upland soil and 110-140 mV for lowland soils.

Tolerant varieties had longer mesocotyls than the controls. Mesocotyl length is closely correlated with seedling establishment (Table 2). Percent and rate of germination of tolerant varieties were significantly higher than those of control varieties (98 and 94%, and 0.97 and 0.93, respectively), although they did not correlate with seedling establishment (Table 2).

The varietal trait of tolerance for anaerobic seeding is expressed in different soils. Incorporating this tolerance into modern varieties is a prerequisite for establishing anaerobic seeding technology. ■